

Public Goods Games in Disease Evolution and Spread

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Abstract

Cooperation arises in nature at every scale, from within cells to entire ecosystems. In the framework of evolutionary game theory, public goods games (PGGs) are used to analyse scenarios where individuals can cooperate or defect, and can predict when and how these behaviours emerge. However, too few examples motivate the transfer of knowledge from one application of PGGs to another. Here, we focus on PGGs arising in disease modelling of cancer evolution and the spread of infectious diseases. We use these two systems as case studies for the development of the theory and applications of PGGs, which we succinctly review and compare. We also posit that applications of evolutionary game theory to decision-making in cancer, such as interactions between a clinician and a tumour, can learn from the PGGs studied in epidemiology, where cooperative behaviours such as quarantine and vaccination compliance have been more thoroughly investigated. Furthermore, instances of cellular-level cooperation observed in cancers point to a corresponding area of potential interest for modellers of other diseases, be they viral, bacterial or otherwise. We aim to demonstrate the breadth of applicability of PGGs in disease modelling while providing a starting point for those interested in quantifying cooperation arising in healthcare.

Keywords: evolutionary game theory | public goods game | cancer | epidemics

1 Introduction

Interactions between individuals amidst an ever-changing environment provide nature with immense complexity. Modelling essential features of evolution, such as selection for advantageous traits, can in part be reduced to interrelations between entities—which can range in scale from subcellular molecules to entire organisms belonging to the same or different species. Evolutionary game theory (EGT) inspects interactions within a population, translating the payoffs of game theory into evolutionary fitness [1]. In this framework, players are not overtly rational, and strategies (types) are inherited according to principles of Darwinian evolution rather than rationally chosen. Consequently, natural selection leads to changes in the frequency of strategies depending

33 on their relative fitness [2]. Some of these strategies, at first glance, seem to contradict Darwinian selection: for
 34 instance, the emergence of behaviours favouring the group over the individual [3].

35 Despite natural selection being centred on competition, cooperative behaviour and relationships arise across
 36 nature. Symbiosis can take many forms, such as services like protection (e.g., plant-ant [4]) or reproductive
 37 services (e.g., pollination [5] or seed dispersal [6]), often in exchange for resources like food or nutrients [7–9].
 38 It can also be found at the microscale: for instance, eukaryotes evolved from primitive unicellular organisms
 39 (including the predecessors to mitochondria), once capable of independent existence, via a cooperative process
 40 called endosymbiosis [10–12]. Because cooperation is an overarching theme across the scales of organisation,
 41 EGT provides a methodological path towards a deeper understanding of evolutionary processes.

42 While cooperation may arise via many different mechanisms [13], the issues surrounding allocations of
 43 resources and distributions of costs are common. This is aptly described by public goods games (PGGs),
 44 where individuals can contribute to a public good, which they then benefit from, regardless of whether they
 45 contributed or not [14]. The two-player version of a PGG is perhaps the most well-known game: the Prisoner’s
 46 Dilemma (PD), introduced in an experiment by Dresher and Flood, named by Tucker [15, 16] and used to
 47 study cooperation for decades [17]. Both of these will be more formally introduced in the following section, as
 48 this paper surveys their use in a prominent area of mathematical biology: disease modelling.

49 Two significant applications of mathematical modelling in healthcare are the spread of pathogens and cancer
 50 evolution. Both of these have been widely described with a variety of methods. For instance, population dynam-
 51 ics can be explored with differential equations [18, 19], agent-based models [20, 21], or stochastic processes [22,
 52 23], whereas including social structure involves borrowing tools from network science [24]. Notably, PGGs can
 53 be applied in many contexts, albeit in different ways: the social aspects of epidemiology lend themselves to
 54 the emergence of cooperative behaviour via implementations such as quarantine or vaccination mandates [25].
 55 On the other hand, cells that evolve to be cancerous are both defecting from the healthy population [26] and
 56 cooperating with one another in support of the new entity called the tumour [27], whose cells are sometimes
 57 even considered a distinct species [28–30]. In reviewing these two areas, we will discuss the appearance of PGGs
 58 and discuss some ways in which each domain may be able to inform the other.

59 2 Public Goods Games

60 In the context of EGT, PGGs are used to study how cooperative strategies arise or collapse over time. The
 61 dynamics that emerge showcase the tension between the benefit of the group and the self-interests of individu-
 62 als [31]. In this game, we consider a group of N players, each endowed with a resource c , which they can invest
 63 in a public pool (a strategy called Cooperate) or not (a strategy called Defect). The total investment within
 64 the group is then multiplied by a factor r , where $1 < r < N$, and distributed back to all players, regardless of
 65 individual contribution (see Figure 1a). If n_c players cooperate, the payoff of a defector is $P_d = rcn_c/N$, and
 66 that of a cooperator is $P_c = P_d - c$ since the cooperators incur the additional cost of investing in the public
 67 good [32]. Note that in many biological processes, the benefit of growth factors is not linear (that is, r is not a
 68 constant in n_c/N). Nevertheless, though there are incentives for players to invest for the benefit of the group,
 69 there also exist incentives to free ride off of others’ contributions [31, 33] (see Figure 1b). A rise in the frequency
 70 of defectors may lead to a phenomenon commonly referred to as the “tragedy of the commons”, where selfish
 71 behaviour leads to a depletion of the common good [34].

72 When $N = 2$, the PGG can be formulated as the PD [17, 35–37]. Similarly to the multiplayer game,
 73 cooperation involves costs c (equivalent to the net cost $c - rc/N$ in the PGG) and brings a benefit b (equivalent
 74 to rc/N in the PGG), which are symmetric to both players. Assuming that $b > c > 0$, this game can be
 75 summarised by the matrix representation in Table 1.

		Player 2	
		Cooperate	Defect
Player 1	Cooperate	$b - c$	$-c$
	Defect	b	0

Table 1: The matrix representing the payoffs received by Player 1 with respect to its strategies and the strategies of Player 2 in the Prisoner’s Dilemma.

76 Historically, the emergence of cooperation was examined with well-mixed population models that assume
 77 all-to-all interactions [38]. Nevertheless, these models fail to capture the complexity of real-life interactions [39].
 78 Introducing networks into the framework of EGT allows for the inclusion of some of those complexities, like
 79 spatial and temporal structure or social relations. Individuals are then represented as nodes and interactions as
 80 edges. Players interact locally with their neighbours, either with one at a time, in two-player games, or with all

Figure 1: **(a)** In public good games, individuals are presented with a choice to either contribute an amount c to a common pot (Cooperate) or not (Defect). All contributions are then multiplied by a factor r (in the example depicted, $r = 2$) and shared equally amongst all players, regardless of their contribution. Hence, a temptation to free ride arises, as defectors still benefit from the public good without incurring the contribution cost. **(b)** Cooperators sustain a cost to supply the whole population with the public good; however, defectors can take advantage of this public good and not suffer said cost. Thus, defectors have an evolutionary advantage, as their payoff (P_d) is always higher than the cooperators' payoff ($P_c < P_d$). Subsequently, a defector introduced in a population of cooperators would be favoured by selection and reproduce faster, eventually leading to their fixation in the population.

81 neighbours simultaneously, in N -player games. Strategies are updated according to a specified rule (of which
 82 there are many [40]), allowing for successful ones to spread.

83 By studying various network structures, it has been shown that the interaction topology impacts strategy
 84 evolution [41]. For example, the spread of cooperation in the PD varies across lattice [42, 43], small-world [44],
 85 regular [45], and real-world networks [46]. The impact of other topological aspects of networks on coopera-
 86 tion has been studied: some examples include the average degree of the network [47], the degree distribution
 87 heterogeneity [48], the presence of hubs on scale-free networks [49], as well as the strategic placement of cooper-
 88 ators [50]. Likewise, when considering PGGs with more than two players, introducing an interaction structure
 89 influences the emergence of cooperation. This holds without considering additional features and when incorpo-
 90 rating mechanisms such as punishment strategies, reputation, voluntary participation, or social diversity. This
 91 has been demonstrated, for instance, on lattice networks [51–53], as well as on regular graphs and heterogeneous
 92 scale-free networks [54, 55].

93 Additionally, multilayer networks can represent multiple types of interactions and individuals, add temporal
 94 and spatial context or depict communities [56, 57]. They are shown to have a significant impact on the
 95 evolutionary dynamics and can promote the evolution of cooperation in the PD [58, 59], multiplayer PGGs [60]
 96 and when several games are present [61–63].

97 3 Applications

98 PGG models have found applications in both epidemiology and oncology, two crucial areas of public health.
 99 Game theoretic tools have been used for decades to study infectious diseases [64] and cancer [65, 66]. Spurred
 100 by the recent COVID-19 pandemic and high incidence rates of cancer worldwide, they have been used even more
 101 widely in these areas. Here, we focus on the appearance of PGGs in both contexts by reviewing the literature
 102 and suggesting ways the two fields may learn from one another.

103 3.1 Epidemics

104 Epidemiology is the study of the distribution and determinants of health-related events in populations [67].
 105 With the help of mathematical models, one can monitor the occurrence of infectious diseases and the course

106 of epidemics, help design public health responses and plan for future incidences. Though Kermack and McK-
107 endrick’s susceptible-infected-recovered (SIR) model [68] is almost a century old, the first appearance of a game
108 theoretical model in epidemiology was in 2004, when Bauch and Earn (2004) described a vaccination game [64].
109 Since then, many PGGs have been used to model epidemiological phenomena, from herd immunity to antibiotic
110 resistance, as well as non-pharmaceutical interventions like social distancing and mask mandates, as shown in
111 Table 2. Importantly, social interactions can be incorporated in each case by adding structure to the populations.

Public good	Cooperate	Defect
Herd immunity (e.g. [69])	Immunisation	Susceptibility
Pathogen-free environment (e.g. [70])	Following non-pharmaceutical interventions, such as mask mandates or social distancing	Not following non-pharmaceutical interventions
Sensitivity to antibiotics (e.g. [71])	Not overusing antibiotics	Overusing antibiotics

Table 2: Examples of public goods found in epidemiological modelling, with corresponding cooperating and defecting strategies.

112 Herd immunity is established within a population when a sufficiently large fraction has undergone immuni-
113 sation, either naturally or via vaccination, ensuring that the disease cannot persist as an endemic condition [19].
114 Because it safeguards individuals against the onset of infectious diseases and is both non-excludable and non-
115 rivalrous, herd immunity can be conceptualised as a public good [69]. Through this lens, immune individuals
116 are cooperators, and those susceptible are defectors. If enough of the population is immune—that is, if n_c/N is
117 greater than some threshold, typically around 90% [69]—the potential drawbacks linked to getting vaccinated
118 may surpass the risks posed by the actual infection. As a result, a free riding strategy may be favoured by
119 some individuals (see Figure 2a). When sufficiently many contributors are necessary for the public good to be
120 reaped, such as in the vaccination game with herd immunity, it is called a threshold PGG [72]. The game can
121 be introduced into classical SIR-type models to better understand individual behaviour in the face of voluntary
122 vaccination [25]. These models can be further enriched by introducing an incubation period between infection
123 and symptom onset. Soltanolkottabi *et al.* (2020) show that the inclusion of this time delay can fundamentally
124 change the epidemic dynamics, leading to fewer vaccinated and free riding individuals and more infections [73].
125 The model also includes a community structure wherein individuals get vaccinated when their (vaccinated)
126 neighbours obtain a higher payoff. Fu *et al.* (2011) relax that assumption, introducing uncertainty into the de-
127 cision to vaccinate. The model showcases social structure’s ability to either promote voluntary vaccinations or
128 facilitate disease spread [74]. Wang *et al.* (2020) further investigate the motivation behind vaccination decisions.
129 Two reasons are considered for getting vaccinated: conforming and increasing one’s payoff. A multilayer network
130 approach then decouples the epidemic dynamics from the vaccination behaviour and captures the multi-levelled
131 nature of human interactions [75]. These results display the importance of individual motivation and social
132 structure in vaccination campaigns.

133 PGGs have also been used to model other dilemmas arising in the wake of epidemics, such as wearing
134 masks [76, 77] and quarantining [78]. Here, rather than herd immunity, the pathogen-free environment can be
135 seen as a public good [70]. For example, Traulsen *et al.* (2023) highlight the importance of individual preference
136 in designing intervention campaigns, including mask mandates, social distancing and vaccinations [79]. Hence,
137 real-world dynamics depend greatly on players’ perceptions of payoffs and risks associated with becoming
138 infected or vaccinating. It is therefore crucial for accurate modelling to consider payoff calibration depending
139 on players’ properties like demographics, location, frequency of interactions and attitude towards vaccination,
140 as well as properties of the disease itself [80–82].

141 Although the whole population can enjoy public goods, sometimes the underlying PGGs are played only
142 by a fraction of the individuals. In the case of antibiotic resistance evolution, those individuals are clinicians,
143 and the public good in question is the sensitivity to antibiotics [71]. From the point of view of a doctor, it
144 is always better to treat their patient with antibiotics, even when the diagnosis is uncertain. However, drug
145 overuse accelerates the evolution of resistance, leading to the tragedy of the commons [71]. Thus, PGGs can
146 model the use of antibiotics and provide insight into possible strategies to avoid antibiotic overuse and resistance
147 evolution [83–85].

148 3.2 Cancer

149 Cancers are evolutionary diseases initiated in a process termed carcinogenesis, in which normal cells transform
150 into malignant tumour cells [86]. EGT models have been used to study interactions occurring during disease
151 progression and treatment at different scales: between cancer cells and cancer cells [87], cancer cells with the
152 tumour microenvironment [88, 89], and cancer cells with the physician [90]. In particular, frequency-dependent

Figure 2: **(a)** During an epidemic, policy-makers are faced with implementing intervention policies aiming at disease containment and eradication. These approaches include vaccines as well as non-pharmaceutical interventions such as mask mandates, lockdowns, etc. PGG models can inform policy-makers by providing insights into how both infectious disease and individual behaviours evolve in the population. Here, defecting individuals are shown in red and cooperating individuals in blue. **(b)** Within the complex tumour microenvironment, healthy and cancerous cells are constantly exchanging information and resources. While tumour cells may free ride by not producing some diffusible factors, they can also cooperate amongst themselves. Clinicians can use evolutionary insights from these underlying dynamics to inform their therapeutic protocols.

153 modelling in oncology began with tools from optimal control [91] before being formalised as EGT [65, 66]. One
 154 of its most significant applications has been modelling the emergence of resistance to treatment [27, 92]. In
 155 particular, PGGs have been used to study the evolution of cooperation in cancer, both from the perspective of
 156 cancer cells defecting from the healthy population as well as cooperation amongst the cancer cells themselves [93],
 157 as depicted in Table 3.

Public good	Cooperate	Defect
Growth factors (e.g. [94])	Producing growth factors (cancerous or healthy cells)	Not producing (only cancer cells)
Other diffusible factors, such as those promoting neoangiogenesis or disabling an immune response (e.g. [95])	Producing diffusible factors	Not producing
Adhesion (e.g. [93])	Producing adhesion molecules	Not producing

Table 3: Examples of public goods found in cancer modelling, with corresponding cooperating and defecting cell types.

158 Carcinogenesis can be viewed as cancer cells free riding on a homeostatic (i.e. under regulation to maintain
 159 stability), healthy population; this has led to cancer cells being sometimes called “cheater cells” [26]. On
 160 the other hand, an established tumour can also be modelled as a collection of cooperating subclones [96].
 161 Many cancer processes rely on the production of diffusible signalling factors by the cancer cells to promote
 162 growth [97] (see Figure 2b). However, producing these factors comes with a cost, such that it is often beneficial
 163 for an individual to free ride on the resources produced by others. Here, the benefit of growth factors is often
 164 nonlinear, modelled as sigmoidal in concentration [98]. For example, Archetti *et al.* (2015) modelled insulin-like
 165 growth factor II (IGF-II) as a public good amongst pancreatic cancer cells in mice. This led to coexistence
 166 between cooperators (producers of IGF-II) and defectors (non-producers), whose bistability was predicted by
 167 PGG dynamics [94].

168 Beyond growth factors shared amongst cancer cells, other diffusible factors such as those promoting neoan-
 169 giogenesis (the production of new blood vessels to supply the tumour with resources such as oxygen) or those
 170 disabling the immune system [99] can be considered public goods. Axelrod *et al.* (2006) argue that this kind
 171 of cellular-level cooperation between partially transformed tumour cells is possible because several hallmarks

172 of cancer—sustaining proliferative signalling, inducing angiogenesis, and activating tissue invasion and metas-
173 tasis [97]—involve shareable resources [95]. Threshold PGGs can also model direct contact between cells and
174 their neighbours. Here, the public good (adhesion between cells) is provided so long as a minimum number of
175 cells contribute adhesion molecules [93].

176 Moreover, Archetti (2021) has proposed leveraging cooperation amongst cancer cells to improve treatment.
177 Genetically engineering some cancer cells to free ride (by not producing a certain growth factor) led to a decrease
178 in the proliferation rate of the tumour population [100]. Hence, PGGs could join other evolutionary concepts in
179 mathematical oncology that have led to novel treatment strategies such as adaptive [101, 102], double-bind [103]
180 and extinction therapies [104, 105].

181 4 Discussion

182 Mathematical models in epidemiology and oncology can inform public health officials and clinicians in their
183 quest to manage and eradicate infectious diseases and cancers. The evolution of tumours and the spread of
184 pathogens have been studied with PGGs; however, their uses have been fairly disjoint. Here, we outline some
185 opportunities for future avenues of research.

186 The evolution of resistance is a central issue in both fields: cancers not eradicated with a first line of
187 therapy are prone to decreasing treatment sensitivity [106]; likewise, antibiotic resistance threatens one’s ability
188 to eliminate pathogenic bacteria [107]. Just as sensitivity to antibiotics is a public good to a population of
189 (possibly infected) individuals (see Table 2), therapeutic sensitivity can be thought of as a public good within
190 a cancer cell population. In both cases, resistance is positively selected for when treatment is applied. On the
191 other hand, it has been shown that bacteria resistant to antibiotics can help shield their sensitive counterparts,
192 increasing the survival capability of the whole population [108]. With these parallels in mind, recall Archetti’s
193 engineered defector cells and their role in collapsing intratumour cooperation [100]. Such a defecting population
194 will spread in the cancer population under clonal selection. If this subclone could be kept sensitive to a certain
195 treatment, then once it subsumes the cooperating population, the tumour might have a better chance of being
196 eradicated by said treatment. Similarly, in epidemiology, one might create a strain of bacteria that doesn’t
197 produce a certain metabolite [109], thus defecting in the PGG though not evolving antibiotic resistance.

198 Introducing network structure in EGT models allows for more accurate representations of real-world dy-
199 namics [110]. For instance, knowledge of the underlying social network during an epidemic can help identify the
200 most influential individuals to vaccinate [111]. However, during dynamical processes—such as the evolution and
201 spread of diseases—these structures are rarely static [112] and often co-evolve with the strategies [113, 114] or
202 even independently [115, 116]. Another class of spatial models considers individuals moving through networks,
203 allowing for the inclusion of complex, ever-changing social interaction patterns [117]. As such, tools from evolu-
204 tioning network theory can sharpen current EGT models. Much like in mathematical epidemiology, the inclusion
205 of spatial structure in cancer models impacts the evolution of cooperation [118–120] (as reviewed in [27]) and
206 could also benefit from dynamical networks.

207 Another recent addition to EGT that shows promise to improve treatment modelling are Stackelberg games,
208 which can describe the leader-follower dynamics between a clinician and a tumour. Here, the cancer cells are
209 themselves also playing an evolutionary game, which allows the clinician to apply evolutionarily-informed treat-
210 ments by anticipating the evolution of the disease [121, 122]. This two-layer framework may find parallels with
211 epidemiological modelling: policy-makers involved in infectious disease response can be considered the leader
212 whose knowledge of the evolving epidemic informs their decision-making. For example, targeting vaccinations
213 can be optimised in pursuit of the public good of herd immunity [123]. Stackelberg evolutionary game theory
214 may help formalise these optimal control problems in both cancer and epidemic modelling.

215 PGGs appear in many areas of mathematical biology and point to unexpected connections between disparate
216 fields of research. Though game theoretic models are informative in understanding the key interactions within a
217 system, real-world data is nevertheless crucial to effectively translate theoretical insights into practical applica-
218 tions. As mathematical modelling in healthcare matures, active discourse between theoreticians, experimenters,
219 clinicians and policy-makers is vital to ensure appropriate model predictions and health interventions.

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230 Conceptualisation (all authors), Writing – Original Draft (all authors), Writing – Review & Editing (all authors),
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232 **Competing interests**

233 The authors declare no competing interests.

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